

ЭНДОКРИННЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЕ В ПРАКТИКЕ СЕМЕЙНОГО ВРАЧА И СТОМАТОЛОГА**Ибрагимов М.А.***кандидат медицинских наук, доцент**Кафедра «Семейной медицины»,**Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет, г.Баку***Ибрагимова Л.К.***ассистент**Кафедра «Терапевтической стоматологии»,**Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет, г.Баку***Гусейнова Р.Н.***ассистент**Кафедра «Терапевтической стоматологии»,**Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет, г.Баку***ENDOCRINE DISEASES IN PRACTICE OF A FAMILY DOCTOR AND DENTIST****Ibrahimov M.,***Candidate of Medical Sciences, assistant professor,**Department of Family Medicine, Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku***Ibrahimova L.,***assistant,**Department of "Therapeutic Dentistry", Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku***Huseynova R.***assistant,**Department of "Therapeutic Dentistry", Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku***АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье рассмотрена важная роль совместной работы семейного врача и стоматолога в профилактике проявлений сахарного диабета 2-го типа в полости рта. Сахарный диабет в настоящее время является весьма распространенным эндокринным заболеванием. У этого заболевания множество симптомов, и некоторые из них можно обнаружить в полости рта. Очень часто сахарный диабет диагностируется случайно, больные могут не обращать внимания на появившиеся у них симптомы, особенно в полости рта пока они не станут более серьезными. Сахарный диабет обычно сопровождается стоматологическими заболеваниями, поэтому стоматологу и семейному врачу необходимо знать все возможные начальные проявления данного грозного заболевания в полости рта, для своевременной постановки диагноза [1]. В настоящее время для профилактики и лечения этой болезни требуются совместные усилия семейного врача и стоматолога [2].

ABSTRACT

This article considers an important role of collaboration between a family doctor and a dentist in the prevention of oral manifestations of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Diabetes mellitus is currently a very wide spread endocrine disease. It has many oral manifestations. Very often, diabetes mellitus is diagnosed accidentally; patients may not pay attention to the symptoms, especially oral signs until they become more serious. Diabetes mellitus is usually accompanied by dental diseases, so the dentist and family doctor need to know all the possible initial oral manifestations of this terrible disease in order to make a timely diagnosis [1]. Currently, the prevention and treatment of diabetes mellitus requires the conjoint efforts of a family doctor and a dentist [2].

Ключевые слова: эндокринные заболевания, сахарный диабет, профилактика, ксеростомия, пародонтит, семейный врач, стоматолог.

Keywords: endocrine diseases, diabetes mellitus, prevention, xerostomia, periodontitis, family doctor, dentist.

Introduction.

According to prognosis of the World Diabetes Federation, the number of patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus will only increase, by 2030 their number will be approximately 552 million people [3]. It should also be taken into account that many people do not even realize that they have this disease. All this indicates the relevance of the problem in preventing this disease [4].

The causes for the wide spread of this disease based on the lifestyle of modern people. Poor nutrition

(eating by standing; snacking; foods containing high fats and carbohydrates), hipodynamia, stress, smoking, alcohol - all these are factors that contribute to the development of type 2 diabetes. Poor ecology and genetics also contribute to its development [5].

Timely diagnosis of this disease is the first step to defeating it. The family doctor needs to know all the possible oral symptoms of diabetes mellitus [6]. Timely prevention of these manifestations will help to avoid many complications, such as periodontitis. The dentist

also must have this knowledge in order to promptly refer the patient to the family doctor for diagnosis. Only their collective work on early diagnosis and prevention will allow getting good results from treatment and preventing possible complications.

Materials and methods. Numerous scientific works due to type 2 diabetes mellitus were the materials for the research. Publications devoted to the oral manifestations of this disease were analyzed and discussed. Analysis and synthesis became the methods in this work.

Research results.

Most scientists have concluded that if diabetes mellitus is not controlled, the risk of developing dental diseases such as periodontitis, dental caries, tooth loss, and xerostomia increases [7].

In reception of patients, both the dentist and the family doctor may encounter patient complaints about oral changes. These alterations may be the first symptoms of diabetes mellitus. Thanks to them, the specialist can quickly and promptly establish the correct diagnosis. Taking into account the prevalence of this disease, we can conclude that oral manifestations are the fastest and most effective way to diagnose type 2 diabetes mellitus [8].

One of the first signs of diabetes mellitus is mouth dryness [9]. Dental caries is also common in this disease [10]. In patients with type 2 diabetes, posterior teeth are susceptible to dental caries, and their recurrent injury is also possible [11]. One of the symptoms manifested in the oral cavity is a white plaque on the tongue [12]. Leosh V.I. and other authors say that patients usually complain of bleeding and pain in the gums, and bad breath [13]. Skiba A.V. also noticed swelling of the gums, accompanied by redness, and small hemorrhages on the palate [14]. Most often, in patients moderate or severe periodontitis are observed [15; 16; 17]. WHO presented statistics according to which 90% of the world's inhabitants suffer from this disease [18].

In periodontitis, it should be taken into account that it can have a negative effect on the organism, worsening the course of the underlying disease – diabetes mellitus, by increasing the level of glycemia. Based on this, it is clear that in the treatment of oral manifestations, cooperation between the dentist and the family doctor is necessary [19].

In treatment of periodontitis, dentists often do not take into account the changes that occur in the organism during type 2 diabetes. Typically, standard treatment is ineffective in this case. Family doctor also does not always refer the patient for a preventive examination to the dentist, and this in the future can lead to the manifestation of endocrine disease in the oral cavity [20].

The family doctor should know that with this disease the patient needs more careful oral care, the use of special pastes and rinses [21]. Based on the above mentioned, we can conclude that in the treatment of diabetes mellitus, the family doctor and the dentist must constantly interact with each other.

According to multiple researches, most people are unaware that symptoms of diabetes mellitus can occur in the mouth. Some dentists also do not take into ac-

count that frequent dental problems occur in people suffering from this disease. They also underestimate the impact of periodontal diseases on the general somatic disease [22].

Prevention of oral manifestations of general somatic diseases is of great importance [23]. The family doctor and the dentist must constantly collaborate. They can develop special recommendations and materials that people with diabetes mellitus should adhere to when caring for their oral cavity. Most patients do not know that there are special pastes and products recommended for their illness. Educational lectures will help in this matter. Also, doctors should determine among themselves the frequency of patients' visits to the dentist for preventive examinations [24].

Conclusion.

Diabetes mellitus has become as an epidemic disease of the 21st century. The danger of this disease is also related to the fact that a person may not be aware of it. This disease is usually diagnosed accidentally or when serious symptoms appear. This disease affects the entire organism and the oral cavity as well. Frequent dental diseases can be the first diagnostic signs of the disease [25]. A dentist who discovers these manifestations must certainly refer the patient to a family doctor to confirm the diagnosis. The family doctor, who also observes them, is obliged to refer the patient to a dentist for treatment of oral manifestations of disease. Only through their collective efforts can the disease itself and its symptoms be prevented and cured. These doctors should work to prevent the occurrence of these manifestations, mainly by educating the population. Their conjoint activities will help reduce the number of patients with oral manifestations in diabetes mellitus.

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